

Animal Vocalization Analysis and Synthesis

Aram Estiu Graugés

MASTER THESIS UPF / 2014
Master in Sound and Music Computing

Master thesis supervisors:
Dr. Jordi Bonada and Dr. Jordi Janer
Department of Information and Communication Technologies
Universitat Pompeu Fabra, Barcelona

Copyright: 2014 Aram Estiu Graugés. This is an open-access document distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License 3.0 Unported, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

Acknowledgements

This thesis could not have been possible without the help of many people but it has been done so first of all I would like to give thanks to the whole Music Technology Group (MTG) for all their teachings and help. Specially to Prof. Xavier Serra for giving me the possibility of joining the SMC and for his inspiring ideas and believings, to Prof. Jordi Bonada and Prof. Jordi Janer for his patience and collaboration in the whole process of this thesis, and last but not least to Prof. Emilia Gómez for guiding and advising me when it was needed, without her SMCers would be quite lost. Apart from them there are many names that I could mention but the list would be incredibly long, thanks to all the people that I have crossed in this two years, thanks for all the teachings and sharing of knowledge.

I owe my deepest gratitude to the SMC crew, in this two years I have met some of the most interesting and opened people who have helped me to reach my goal, specially to the ones that have shared the whole way and the suffering with me *Oriol, Roger* and *Urbez*. Also I want to mention some of my spiritual gurus who have inspired me in several occasions, *Rob, Nadine, Andres, Jakue, Felipe, Tobé, Toros, Emre* and all the others.

Lastly I would like to thank my family and friends for all his support and motivation in this work, thank you for make me like I am, my love is for you.

To all the people that I have mentioned and the ones I forgot,
Thank you very much.

Abstract

This Master's thesis focuses on the unexplored domain of animal vocalizations. In the present work Lemur (madagascarian mammal) vocalizations are studied and analysed in order to create a system that can process and train datasets and posteriorly synthesize vocalizations. To achieve the goal the technique of Hidden Markov Models based synthesis is used with the HMM-based speech synthesis system (HTS) toolbox, based on the wide known Hidden Markov Model Toolkit (HTK) speech recognition system. In the following pages a system to synthesize lemur vocalizations is presented and its advantages and inconveniences defined.

Contents

Index of figures	viii
1 INTRODUCTION	1
2 STATE OF THE ART	2
2.1 Animal Vocalizations	2
2.2 Lemur Vocalizations	4
2.2.1 Lemur Phonatory System	4
2.2.2 Lemur Vocalizations studies	5
2.3 Analysis Techniques	12
2.3.1 Human Speech Analysis Techniques	13
2.3.2 Animal Vocalizations Analysis	18
2.4 Synthesis Techniques	21
2.4.1 Animal Vocalization Synthesis using HMM	21
2.4.2 Open Source Tools	23
3 METHODOLOGY	24
3.1 Motivation	24
3.2 Training Data	25
3.2.1 Lemurs Dataset	26
3.2.2 Recording Animal Vocalizations	27
3.3 HMM based synthesis	28
3.4 HMM-based Speech Synthesis System (HTS)	32
3.4.1 System adaptation to animal vocalizations	33
4 EVALUATION AND RESULTS	38
4.1 Vocalizations Evaluation	38
4.1.1 Early High Wails	39
4.1.2 Huhs	42
4.1.3 Moan	45
4.1.4 Purr	48

4.2	System Evaluation	56
5	CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK	58
5.1	Contributions	58
5.2	Conclusions	59
5.3	Future Work	59

List of Figures

2.1	Spectrum for the different Indri's vocalizations.	7
2.2	Mean parameters for the Indri's vocalizations.	7
2.3	Spectrogram for the different vowel vocalizations from <i>Varecia Variegata Variegata</i>	9
2.4	Spectrum for the different Crowned Lemur's vocalizations.	11
2.5	Mean parameters for the Crowned Lemur's vocalizations.	12
2.6	Model for speech signals using LPA.	13
2.7	Diagram for Mel Frequency Cepstral Coefficients computation.	15
2.8	PLP modeling of the human hearing system.	16
2.9	PLP model computation steps	17
2.10	An example of a three-state, left-to-right HMM.	18
2.11	Block Diagram for the gPLP feature extraction technique.	19
3.1	Example of a table showing different call features from [Gamba and Giacoma, 2007].	26
3.2	Example of statistics and generated speech parameteres for phonemes /a/ and /i/ from [Tokuda et al., 2013].	30
3.3	HMM-based speech synthesis system from [Tokuda et al., 2002].	34
4.1	The original Vocalization.	40
4.2	The recorded vocalization.	40
4.3	The synthesized vocalization.	40
4.4	Plots of the 3 different <i>Early High Wail</i> signals with its enve- lope on top.	40
4.5	Plot of the energy variation in the 3 different vocalizations.	41
4.6	Plot of the Zero Crossing Rate in the 3 different vocalizations.	41
4.7	The original vocalization.	42
4.8	The recorded vocalization.	42
4.9	Spectral Centroid mean and Spectral Roll Off mean for the <i>Early High Wails</i> samples.	42
4.10	Plot of the Spectral Flux mean in the 3 different vocalizations.	43
4.11	The original Vocalization.	44

4.12	The recorded vocalization.	44
4.13	The synthesized vocalization.	44
4.14	Plots of the 3 different <i>Huhs</i> signals with its envelope on top.	44
4.15	Plot of the energy variation in the 3 different vocalizations.	45
4.16	Plot of the Zero Crossing Rate in the 3 different vocalizations.	45
4.17	The original vocalization.	46
4.18	The recorded vocalization.	46
4.19	Spectral Centroid mean and Spectral Roll Off mean for the <i>Huhs</i> samples.	46
4.20	Plot of the Spectral Flux for the 3 vocalizations.	47
4.21	The original Vocalization.	48
4.22	The recorded vocalization.	48
4.23	The synthesized vocalization.	48
4.24	Plots of the 3 different <i>Moan</i> signals with its envelope on top.	48
4.25	Plot of the energy variation in the 3 different vocalizations.	49
4.26	Plot of the Zero Crossing Rate in the 3 different vocalizations.	49
4.27	The original vocalization.	50
4.28	The recorded vocalization.	50
4.29	Spectral Centroid mean and Spectral Roll Off mean for the <i>Moan</i> samples.	50
4.30	Plot of the Spectral Flux for the 3 vocalizations.	51
4.31	The original Vocalization.	52
4.32	The recorded vocalization.	52
4.33	The synthesized vocalization.	52
4.34	Plots of the 3 different <i>Purr</i> signals with its envelope on top.	52
4.35	Plot of the energy variation in the 3 different vocalizations.	53
4.36	The original vocalization.	54
4.37	The recorded vocalization.	54
4.38	Spectral Centroid mean and Spectral Roll Off mean for the <i>Purr</i> samples.	54
4.39	Plot of the Spectral Flux for the 3 vocalizations.	55

Chapter 1

INTRODUCTION

Speech synthesis is a challenging problem nowadays. Although many advances have been done in the present years, there is still room for improving, the main clue point is the naturality of the synthesis.

There are many researchers involved in the speech synthesis problem so most of the aspects are being developed at the moment. In the last years the HMM-based synthesis techniques have broke into the state of the art extending its influence to almost every research group in the field (a part from extending its power to other fields). The technique is really powerful and effective for modeling phonemes and other speaking units due to the properties of Hidden Markov Models (HMM).

But the work presented in this document tries to find another domain for HMM-based synthesis, the main idea is that most of the mammals share the same phonatory system with humans so if human speech synthesis is working quite good then it can be tried with mammals vocalizations. The point is that synthesizers by samples or other techniques can give realist results but with the handicap of being closed to what is recorded and its combinations. The idea is to apply HMM-based synthesis to animal vocalizations and use the benefits that has this techniques like context modeling, model interpolation or model adaptation to generate realistic samples. Basically a system dedicated to animal vocalization synthesis will be set and its results tested.

Chapter 2

STATE OF THE ART

In this chapter an overview of scientific publications which are related in some way or another to animal vocalizations synthesis are presented. This review is the basis for the work that is developed in this thesis. It must be said that there is not too much work around this topic, but on the other hand the technology that is needed has been already tested and broadly used in other topics.

First, mammal vocalization are analyzed mainly focused on the acoustical parameters. Then this analysis is centered in Lemur vocalizations and expanded with ethology knowledge. After that, techniques for animal vocalization analysis are presented. Finally speech synthesis techniques are presented and the application in the animal vocalization synthesis domain is commented.

2.1 Animal Vocalizations

The study of animal vocalizations is really broad, but it is not directly related to the field of study of this thesis, it is mostly related to biological fields like ethology and evolution. This fields have great interest in mammals, in great part for studying the evolution [Fitch, 2006] of our phonatory system and the communication between other mammals of the same species[Gamba and Giacoma, 2007].

All mammals share common ancestors this means that the organs from different species share a common structure. This can be extrapolated to all tetrapods including mammals, amphibians, reptiles and birds, whose species share a common inheritance. In the phonatory system this is noticed in three key components: a respiratory system with lungs; a larynx that acts primarily as a quick-closing gate protecting the lungs, and secondarily to produce sound; and a supralaryngeal vocal tract which that filters the sound emitted previously [Fitch, 2006]. As the work it is centered in mammals vocalizations the further comments are about the phonatory systems which in some point are similar to the human system, the evolutions

of phonatory systems in different directions will not be commented. Most of the mentioned animals have continued using the system based on the three key items and the voice production system(VPS) can be defined by the long-time studied source/filter theory and other theories more related to biology [Titze, 1994].

If we focus on the acoustic theory of speech involving the source/filter theory speech or vocalizations can be defined as a combination of a source function and a filtering process executed by the vocal-tract [Fant, 1981].

Expanding the explanation from a more biological point of view we can describe the source as the pressure and air stream provided by the lungs and the attendant respiratory musculature. Exclusively in mammals there is the diaphragm which is a very efficient air-pumping system. The air from the source can flow (generating sound) on both directions interior and exterior. After the lungs we find the trachea which is protected by a larynx, this larynx is present in all tetrapods and comes from the gill bars of fish ancestors. The larynx primitively includes sphincter-like musculature and a pair of bar-like cartilages that can be separated or pushed together. This structure can produce one of the most primitive sounds which is a turbulent hiss created by the expulsion of air with the larynx partially closed. In the larynx there are the responsables for the phonation, the vocal folds. They are elastic membranes and they are unique in mammals in the sense that generally include a 'vocalis' or thyroarytenoid muscle [Fitch, 2006]. This last part of the phonatory system combined with the rest of the vocal tract(nose, mouth...) originates the formants due to the resonant frequencies in the different cavities of this vocal tract.

The differences between human and non-human vocal tract were based on the resting position of the larynx which was much lower in adult humans than in non-humans, and while in breathing non-humans could have the larynx inserted into the nasal cavity and humans could not perform it. This difference was used as a limiting factor for non-human vocalizations and contrary to humans none other parts apart from the larynx had not been studied in non-human species.

An other limitation was that the phonatory organs analysis was done to dead mammals, this meant that the tissues were tight and rigid. Recently some studies have been done in different species stating that non-human vocal-tract could be closer to humans than it was suspected some years ago. This means that mammals can lower their larynges apart from other notable improvements on its phonatory system, giving place to a much broad spectrum of formants giving place to vocalizations [Fitch, 2000].

Departing from this point it can be stated that mammals, and precisely primates, have an enough closer phonatory system that can be modeled by the algorithms used for voice or speech synthesis nowadays.

2.2 Lemur Vocalizations

As this document reflects the work done on a Master Thesis it is impossible to cover the whole case of mammal vocalizations. For that reason the thesis will be focused on Lemur vocalizations. The choice of Lemurs comes from the extensive analysis that have been done on this species vocalizations by Prof. Gamba from University of Torino, because there is a big handicap which is that all the Lemur species are endemic from Madagascar.

In this part Lemur acoustical data along with ethological data will be presented, various Lemur species will be mentioned as all the species are part of the same family, all the data may be useful for analyzing and synthesizing its utterances.

2.2.1 Lemur Phonatory System

Lemurs are considered to resemble primitive primates, this means that they are sharing the structure of the phonatory system with humans. The same components are shared between these species although Lemurs do not have lips, so they are unable to perform lip protrusion.

As in humans phonation in Lemurs starts in the larynx with the vibration of the vocal folds, they are opened and closed depending on the air pressure from the lungs and if the pressure conditions are stable they will keep opening and closing at a certain rate that will define the fundamental frequency. This air flows into the next stage, the supralaryngeal vocal tract which is composed by the cavities in the mouth and nose. The nasal and vocal cavity acts as a filter and models the air by reducing the energy in different frequency bands, the bands that keep most of its energy will be the formants [Gamba et al., 2012][Gamba and Giacoma, 2010]. The only component that is not present in humans is the air sac and according to recent studies its usage needs to be studied further [Naish, 2010].

Not many years ago it was considered that non-human primates speech differed from human speech for the lack of continual articulation, but recent studies have changed this paradigm giving non-human primates a much more complex articulatory system than it was thought [Gamba and Giacoma, 2006].

The conclusion from this section is that Lemurs vocalizations as human vocalizations can be modeled using the source-filter model commented on the previous section.

2.2.2 Lemur Vocalizations studies

Most of the Lemur species vocalizations have been widely covered by different authors, in this section a summary of some of these studies is presented, each subsection is dedicated to a different species.

Indri (*Indri Indri*)

The *Indri Indri* is famous for its song, "the indri song". Because it is a characteristic territorial and defence announcement song which can be heard from 3 or 4 kilometers away in the jungles of Madagascar.

Indris possess 8 distinguishable vocal types apart from the indri song vocal content. The description of each vocal type is presented here in order to understand the acoustical nature of each sound and to make a vague idea of the situations where Indris vocalize them.

- Roar
 - Also called bark, it is emitted in series of 2 or more units, usually is not emitted singly. It seems that Indris use them when there are aerial predators and they also occur at the beginning of the indri's song and during honk series. After a roar individuals tend to grasp their vocal sac.
A roar is a loud tonal call, it has harmonic structure merged with noisy component.
- Honk
 - Honks are vocalized in the presence of terrestrial predators. Usually emitted in series of 6 or more with optional roars between them. It is possible to hear the individuals inhaling air between utterances.
It is a loud tonal vocalization with great energy over the harmonics.
- Hum
 - Hums are vocalized during foraging, resting time or during group movements.
It is a guttural, low-pitched with low-intensity vocalization. It is concentrated in the lower frequency bands and it may be emitted alone or in series.
- Short tonal Call

- Short tonal calls are usually emitted during group conflicts where there is physical contact. It is emitted isolated or between long tonal calls. It is a short tonal call with a clear formant structure.
- Long tonal call
 - Long tonal call is emitted in the same situation that the short tonal call. It is longer than the short tonal call and with lower F0 and it is emitted in series. It shows a harmonic structure with clear formants.
- Kiss
 - Kiss are used as a rejection answer to contact, normally in fear or anxiety situations. It is also emitted in alert state followed by a wheeze. Similar to a human kiss it has low harmonics content with a decreasing progression. It is vocalized alone.
- Wheeze
 - Wheeze is emitted in the second step of the so called *cri d'amour*, after the kiss. It is also emitted in competitive intra-group situations or when there is a dangerous situation. It is a short low-intensity call with low harmonic component and it is emitted alone.
- Grunt
 - Grunt is uttered when the individuals are frightened or anxious or during aggressive behaviour or as a warning call. It is composed by a series of low-pitched sounds.

For better understanding of the acoustical features of the *Indri Indri* vocalization two figures (with its original description) from the original paper [Maretti et al., 2010] where all the information has been extracted from. The first one (figure 2.1) shows the spectrums of the different vocalizations and the second one (figure 2.2) shows the mean parameters which its variation.

Figure 2.1: Spectrum for the different Indri's vocalizations.

Fig. 1 - Sound spectrograms of Indri indri vocal types: Roar (a), honk (b, anticipated by voiced inhalation), hum (c), short tonal call (d), long tonal call (e), kiss (f), wheeze (g), grunt (h), infant calls (hum, iI; contact-seeking call, iII; grunt, iIII) and the indri song (j, showing introductory roars). All spectrograms were generated in Praat 5.1.15 (www.praat.org) with the following parameters: window length: 0.02 sec, time range as shown (max. 0-62 sec); frequency range: 0-12000 Hz; maximum: 100 dB/Hz; dynamic range: 30-55 dB; dynamic compression: 0.0.

Figure 2.2: Mean parameters for the Indri's vocalizations.

Tab. 3 - Mean and standard deviation of the acoustic parameters per vocal type. Number of calls we have analysed is reported after the vocal type (N). Parameters we measured were: duration (DUR), average fundamental frequency (MeF0), maximum fundamental frequency (MaF0), minimum fundamental frequency (MiF0), average first formant (F1), second formant (F2) and third formant (F3).

Vocalization	DUR (s)	MeF0 (Hz)	MaF0 (Hz)	MiF0 (Hz)	F1 (Hz)	F2 (Hz)	F3 (Hz)
Roar (24)	0.86±0.37	269±39	322±42	243±39	733±106	1512±121	2879±250
Honk (94)	0.26±0.09	637±28	654±23	614±46	1060±142	1918±136	3357±443
Hum (632)	0.49±0.37	133±50	159±48	106±54	568±332	1585±398	2254±159
Long Tonal Call (23)	0.36±0.30	276±67	318±61	249±77	798±278	2442±487	4218±400
Short Tonal Call (17)	0.17±0.08	533±131	584±120	488±155	1918±575	4459±608	7080±539
Kiss (61)	0.09±0.04	584±77	600±73	567±88	1202±221	2982±382	4547±281
Wheeze (51)	0.37±0.13	814±317	858±327	764±305	1838±646	4099±778	6399±898
Grunt (768)	0.06±0.05	137±51	140±50	133±52	923±635	3038±545	4409±412

Black and White Ruffed Lemur *Varecia Variegata Variegata*

The Black and White Ruffed Lemur is supposed to be the most studied in terms of the vocal repertoire [Gamba and Giacoma, 2006]. 16 vocal types have been recognized [Pereira et al., 1988] but in this section only 4 vowel utterances plus a non vocalic one are presented due to the inaccessibility of the paper. The description of the vocalizations is presented here.

- Mew
 - Mews are emitted in relaxed contest but also mother Lemurs emit them to communicate with the newborn Lemurs.
It is a tonal vocalization and usually shows a moderate to absent frequency modulation. In adult individuals a slow rise in pitch is present.
- Shriek
 - Shriek is a part of the Roar Shriek Chorus which is a group call.
It is a narrow-band frequency modulated vocalization.
- Roar
 - Roar is the first part of the Roar Shriek Chorus and is the only non-vocalic vocalization.
It is a wide-band noisy sound.
- Wail
 - Wails are used when there is a need for re-aggregation and it is only emitted at the end of the Roar Shriek Chorus.
It is rich in high harmonics and tonal but it can also contain a noisy component.
- Growl-Snort
 - Growl-Snort is a call that is emitted as a reaction from a disturbance.
It is a very low-pitched emission followed by a fast and noisy expulsion of air.

In figure 2.3 we can see the spectrum of the different vocalizations above (apart from the Roar). All the information above along with the figure has been extracted from [Gamba and Giacoma, 2006].

Figure 2.3: Spectrogram for the different vowel vocalizations from *Varecia Variegata Variegata*.

Figure 1. Sonograms of vocal types Mew (a), Shriek (b), Wail (c) and Growl-Snort (d) emitted by the ruffed lemur (*Varecia variegata variegata*). All spectrograms were generated in Praat with the following parameters: time range: frequency range: 0-12000 Hz; maximum: 100 dB/Hz; dynamic range: 30 dB; pre-emphasis: 6.0 dB/Oct; dynamic compression: 0.0.

Crowned Lemur (*Eulemur coronatus*)

The Crowned Lemur is called like this because females have a bronze spot of fur on the head similar to the shape of a crown. Here a brief description of the its utterances is presented, in total there are 10 different vocalizations.

- Long Grunt
 - Long Grunt is emitted when there is a high level of arousal in the group and is emitted by both sexes.
It is a non-harmonic low-pitched call that has medium intensity. It also shows clearly 5 formants.
- Long Grunt Clear Call
 - This call is emitted when disturbance is high and individuals in the group are upset and very excited. They are emitted by both sexes.
It is similar to the Long Grunt but with a tonal element that shows some frequency modulation at the end.
- Grunted Hoot

- Grunted Hoots are emitted frequently but the context is unknown.
It is a really low-pitched vocalization concentrated in the low bands with low intensity which widens up its spectrum at the end (hoot sound).
- Grunt
 - Grunts are frequently emitted by both sexes. They are emitted in the same situations that in the *Indri Indri*.
It is a short low-pitched vocalization of low intensity.
- Snort
 - Snorts are emitted when Lemurs are agitated and jumping.
It is a low-pitched call with low-intensity and shows 4 formants which are not always clear.
- Click
 - Clicks are emitted in danger situations. They are emitted by males and females but less usually in the latter.
It is a noisy, wide band, really short call.
- Hoot
 - Hoots are low level group alerts.
It is a low-pitched harmonic vocalization.
- Alarm Call
 - As the name says it is emitted with the presence of aerial or terrestrial predators.
The Alarm Call is tonal and shows frequency upsweeps. It shows 4 clear formants.
- Tonal Call
 - Tonal call is emitted for maintaining the contact between the members of the group.
It is a harmonic pitched utterance which keeps stable.
- Scream
 - Screams are emitted by males in presence of females.
It is a high pitched harmonic call that shows modulation and high intensity. 4 formants can be clearly identified.

To understand better the description of the calls two figures are provided. The first one (figure 2.4) contains a spectrum for each one of the vocalizations, and the second one (figure 2.5) contains the mean parameters with the standard deviation for the different vocalizations. All the information above and the figures have been extracted from [Gamba and Giacoma, 2007].

Figure 2.4: Spectrum for the different Crowned Lemur's vocalizations.

Fig. 3. — Sound spectrograms of the vocal types Long Grunt (a), Long Grunt Clear Call (b), Grunted Hoot (c), Grunt (d), Snort (e), Click (f), Hoot (g), Alarm call (h), Tonal Call (j), Scream (k). All spectrograms were generated in Praat with the following parameters: window length: 0.02 sec, time range as shown (0.35-2.80 sec); frequency range: 0-9000 Hz; maximum: 50 dB/Hz; dynamic range: 35-45 dB; pre-emphasis: 6.0 dB/Oct; dynamic compression: 0.0.

Figure 2.5: Mean parameters for the Crowned Lemur’s vocalizations.

Table 2.

Mean and standard deviation of the acoustic parameters per vocal type. Number of average individual values considered is reported after the vocal type (N). Parameters we measured were: duration (DUR), average fundamental frequency (MeF0), minimum fundamental frequency (MiF0), maximum fundamental frequency (MaF0), standard deviation of the fundamental frequency (SdF0), cumulative variation of the fundamental frequency (SV), average first formant (F1), second formant (F3), third formant (F3), fourth formant (F4).

Vocalization	MeF0 (Hz)	MiF0 (Hz)	MaF0 (Hz)	SdF0 (Hz)	SV (Hz)
Long Grunt (5)	62±3	42±2	89±4	13±2	8±4
Long Grunt Clear Call (15)	61±5	46±4	84±7	10±1	12±3
Grunted Hoot (16)	69±3	53±3	88±5	11±2	22±3
Grunt (22)	57±4	49±5	66±4	5±1	11±3
Snort (4)	234±194	107±44	398±423	97±127	147±189
Click (9)	102±6	91±7	114±12	8±5	16±9
Hoot (9)	239±52	183±54	295±41	38±10	72±18
Alarm Call (11)	245±90	144±50	358±138	68±34	69±21
Tonal Call (6)	928±103	747±134	1017±87	74±27	127±44
Scream (14)	3773±884	2064±566	5352±841	1053±164	769±379

Vocalization	DUR (sec)	F1 (Hz)	F2 (Hz)	F3 (Hz)	F4 (Hz)
Long Grunt (5)	0.842±0.136	697±246	2720±458	4804±658	7068±609
Long Grunt Clear Call (15)	0.432±0.053	1184±181	2816±153	4560±246	6784±271
Grunted Hoot (16)	0.169±0.049	394±68	2509±114	4186±121	6500±274
Grunt (22)	0.134±0.045	489±131	2907±207	4519±241	6662±437
Snort (4)	0.304±0.067	866±457	3066±258	4973±366	7570±181
Click (9)	0.090±0.044	777±327	2663±282	4747±301	6794±318
Hoot (9)	0.214±0.064	516±82	2065±354	4455±312	6800±247
Alarm Call (11)	0.502±0.121	1286±373	3261±452	5700±404	8710±408
Tonal Call (6)	0.426±0.074	1148±93	2598±273	4600±386	6917±434
Scream (14)	0.465±0.147	3001±677	7692±798	13351±1016	16967±987

2.3 Analysis Techniques

In this section some of the most interesting analysis techniques for animal vocalizations are presented. As there is not much literature about animal analysis from a sound design point of view, because normally it is investigated from the bioacoustics point of view, first some human speech analysis techniques are described. As it has been seen in previous sections we can consider many similitudes between mammals vocalizations and human speech, at least in the generation process. Another reason is that animals may have a similar emotional tonal perception in vocalizations, there are recent works with dog vocalizations that humans perceive the same emotional content with this vocalizations than with humans vocalizations [Fragó et al., 2014].

After these techniques this section focus on the recent advances in animal vocalization analysis and an other recent technique about animal vocalization enhancement is presented. This last technique is important for the reason that most of the

times animal vocalizations are recorded in noisy environments (Wildness, zoos, groups of individuals...) and this produce that recordings normally contain a lot of background noise which reduces the quality of the interesting sounds.

2.3.1 Human Speech Analysis Techniques

The tecniques presented in this section are useful for vocal description and posterior synthesis. One of the ideas of this algorithms is to extract useful features that permit to extract a proper model from the samples an make possible a posterior reconstruction of the vocalizations.

Linear Predictive Analysis (LPA)

Linear predictive analysis has its strong points in providing accurate estimates of the speech parameters, concretely the spectral envelopment, computing the parameters in a reasonably fast time and last defining a speech sequences with really few data. So it is a perfect candidate for speech modeling.

LPA implements a particular source/filter model, an schema extracted from [Rabiner and Schafer, 2007] is shown in figure 2.6 with the vocal model inside the dashed rectangle.

Figure 2.6: Model for speech signals using LPA.

Mathematically it is a linear system that over shor samples of time is defined by an all-pole system function which you can see in equation 2.1.

$$H(z) = \frac{S(z)}{E(z)} = \frac{G}{1 - \sum_{k=1}^p a_k z^{-k}} \quad (2.1)$$

Excitation is defined by the vocal tract system model as it is any signal needed to produce $s[n]$ the output of the system. As it has been said above an advantatge

of this system is the velocity and effectivity in computing the spectral filter coefficients (a_k) plus the gain parameter (G).

As we can see in fig.2.6 the speech samples $s[n]$ are related to $e[n]$, through the difference equation between them. Then a linear predictor defined by the a_k coefficients outputs his results which are compared to the exactly predict sample. The amount of failure is computed. After this steps what comes out is a FIR linear system defined by eq. 2.2 which is a prediction error filter. This filter results into an inverse filter which can solve our initial system with the predictor coefficients as it is shown in eq. 2.3

$$A(z) = 1 - \sum_{k=1}^p a_k z^{-k} = \frac{D(z)}{S(z)} \quad (2.2)$$

$$H(z) = \frac{G}{A(z)} \quad (2.3)$$

The difficulty in this system is to compute the predictor coefficients, the main idea is to minimize the mean-squared error between in a short speech segment by computing this coefficients at a appropriate rate for capturing the speech variation (50-100 times per second).

Some of the uses of LPA are speech compression, as it can define speech parameters in an efficient and reduced way. Formant analysis is also a trendy application as it defines the power spectrum with these few coefficients. The handicap of LPA is that as the name says it is a linear system on the contrary of human voice this difference may make LPA less effective than other systems [Dave, 2013].

LPA information and definition was extracted from [Rabiner and Schafer, 2007].

Mel Frequency Cepstrum Coefficients (MFCC)

MFCC is a feature extraction method for the cepstral domain. It is of the most prevalent and popular method nowadays.

As its name says it uses the Mel scale which is based on human ear perception. MFCC's are a representation of the cepstral of a short-time windowed signal extracted from the computation of Fast Fourier Transform. A nonlinear frequency scale is used for approximating the behavior of human auditory system.

The technique block diagram can be seen in figure 2.7, and it consists in dividing

the signal into time frames containing an arbitrary number of samples. Overlapping and windowing is used in order to smooth transitions from frame to frame and to keep frame edge continuities. After this process FFT is computed for each frame and frequency content is extracted. Once in the frequency domain Mel-Scaled filter bank is applied to the output of the FFT, the scale is linear up to 1 kHz and logarithmic at greater frequencies, the relation between regular frequencies and Mel scale frequencies is denoted by eq. 2.4.

$$Frequency(MelScaled) = [2595 \log(1 + f(Hz)/700)] \quad (2.4)$$

Finally the Discrete Cosine Transformation (DCT) is computed from the Mel scale filters bank.

Figure 2.7: Diagram for Mel Frequency Cepstral Coefficients computation.

Mel scale transformation enables to keep the same temporal resolution for each band, the output is a set of coefficients for each frame. For all frames a number of coefficients is defined according to the wanted resolution, similarly to LPA.

MFCC's are robust and reliable to variations depending on the recording conditions of the target signal. The emphasis is put on getting parameters similar to the ones that humans use for hearing speech.

All the information and diagram was extracted from [Dave, 2013].

Perceptual Linear Prediction (PLP)

The Perceptual Linear Prediction model is based on the psychophysics of hearing and tries to model human speech according to these parameters. The main idea is to discard irrelevant information according to human perception qualities. PLP uses the same process as LPA except that PLP features are computed according to the psychophysics of human hearing, the model characteristics can be seen in fig. 2.8.

Figure 2.8: PLP modeling of the human hearing system.

As we can see in 2.8 PLP is approximating three main perceptual features which are critical-band resolution curves, equal-loudness curve and the intensity-loudness power-law relation.

In fig. 2.9 we can see the processing steps of this model. First the signal is split into frames, windowed and brought to the spectral domain by the FFT like in previous models. Then a frequency warping according to the Bark scale perceptual model is applied. The correspondance between the Bark scale and the audio frequencies is shown in eq, 2.5

$$\Omega(\omega) = 6 \ln \left(\frac{\omega}{1200\pi} + \left(\left(\frac{\omega}{1200\pi} \right)^2 + 1 \right)^{0.5} \right) \quad (2.5)$$

The warped spectrum is then convoluted with the power spectrum of the simulated critical-band masking curve, to emulate band masking in human hearing. This spectrum is down-sampled at intervals of 1 Bark approximately. This is the first step defined in fig. 2.8 and all this process is integrated in a single filter-bank, the Bark filter bank. After that an equal-loudness simulating process is applied to the outputs emulating in this way human hearing curve, following this process the results are transformed to the power law of Stevens by raising each to the power of 0.33.

The resulting from the previous steps is then processed by Linear Prediction. Here the steps are the same like in LPA with the difference of the perceptual model and is just differenciated because the LPA all-pole model approximates the spectrum bands power equally well for each band, this method is inconsistent to human

hearing perception. PLP processing diagram can be seen in fig. 2.9.

Figure 2.9: PLP model computation steps

This method was developed by Hermansky in the 90's and it has the advantage of modeling speech based on the human hearing system, this provides more real precision and an improvement of speech recognition rate. All the information and figures in this section was extracted from [Dave, 2013] and [Hermansky, 1990].

Hidden Markov Models

Hidden Markov Model (HMM) is a statistical modeling technic based on Markov Models. The difference between the latter and HMM is that this method keeps its states hidden in the sense that just the output of each state is visualized. Each state in HMM has a probability distribution for a particular output therefore the generated data gives a clue on the sequence of transition states.

Each model is characterized by sets of initial-state probabilities, state-transition probabilities and state-output probability distributions. In speech modeling normally just spectral parameters are used while in HMM spectral plus excitation parameters are also used. For the excitation part it uses multispace probability distribution and for the spectral parameters different approaches can be used like MFCC's, LPC's... Each Model also contains for each state the duration probability distribution to model the temporal structure of the source. HMM can also use contextual features, like stress, pitch accent, tone and speech segments information. A HMM model can be defined by eq. 2.6 and eq. 2.7 where $O = [O_1^T, O_2^T, \dots, O_T^T]^T$ and W be a set of speech parameters and corresponding context information, then the states for a HMMModel will be generated out of this information, we can see a representation of a three-state HMMModel in fig. 2.10.

$$\lambda_{max} = \text{argmax}_p(O|\lambda, W) \quad (2.6)$$

$$p(O|\lambda, W) = \sum_{\forall q} \pi_{q_0} \prod_{t=1}^T a_{q_{t-1}q_t} b_{q_t}(O_t) \quad (2.7)$$

Figure 2.10: An example of a three-state, left-to-right HMM.

HMM are used for Automatic Speech Recognition(ASR), music score following, part-of-speech tagging, speech synthesis (which is commented on the synthesis section) and many more usages outside the Signal Processing field. All the information was extracted from [Fosler-lussier, 1998] and [Tokuda et al., 2013].

2.3.2 Animal Vocalizations Analysis

Most of the techniques commented in the previous section 2.3.1 can be used for mammal vocalization analysis as the similarities between most of the species and humans are great as it has been stated before. In recent years acoustic analysis work has been done in the field of bioacoustics. In this section the most recent techniques which are meaningful from a Sound Design point of view are presented.

Generalized Perceptual Linear Prediction (GPLP)

gPLP as it can be seen in the name it is a variation of the PLP technique. As PLP it incorporates Perceptual characteristics in the analysis, gPLP adds psychophysical information about the species that needs to be analyzed.

There are two types of information used one would be the same concept of the Bark scale for human perception but applied to any species, so the frequency hearing range and critical bandwidth of the species; the second data used is an audiogram of the same species. The first data is convoluted with the Power Spectrum in order to smooth and downsample as it was done in the PLP. From the audiogram a filter bank is extracted and it is used for computing the Equal Loudness Normalization. These are the differences between PLP and gPLP, in the fig. 2.11 a block diagram of the processing step is shown.

Figure 2.11: Block Diagram for the gPLP feature extraction technique.

The gPLP extracts perceptually meaningful features from the target species, PLP the coefficients extracted represent the filtering from the vocal tract and can define it with few coefficients. gPLP spectrograms also enhance the spectral peaks and suppress broadband background noise, in animal recordings this characteristic is really useful. gPLP spectrograms are shown to enhance the spectral peaks and suppress broadband background noise. An other advantage for gPLP is that it can be easily modified to be adapted to any species with enough psychophysical information.

All the information from gPLP has been extracted from [Clemins, Patrick J., S.B., 2005], [Clemins and Johnson, 2006] and [Staab, 2014].

Enhancement of Animal Vocalization

As it has been stated in previous sections, animal vocalization recording can be really problematic due to the natural environment of most of the species, few quality recordings can be achieved without background noise or disturbances.

Some enhancement techniques for animal vocalization are briefly presented below and its effectiveness in different animal vocalizations is explained.

- Kalman Filter
 - The Kalman filter has multiple applications in different fields. In this case the interesting application is the usage of the algorithm for speech enhancement, or what is the same noise reduction. The Kalman filter uses a form of feedback control to estimate the disturbing signal and tries to filter it. These feedback control is formed by two steps one that tries to predict how the disturbance will evolve and the other that corrects the signal. These feedback loop is repeated through the whole signal and keeps updating the parameters that control the two steps. Summary extracted from [Welch and Bishop, 1997].
- Spectral Subtraction
 - Spectral subtraction is a non-parametric technique which tries to estimate the noise in the spectrum, this estimation is typically done during periods of speaker silence. This estimated noise is subtracted from the original signal trying to delete the noise presence in the frequential domain. After that the signal without the noise is brought to the temporal domain with the IFFT.
- Wavelet Analysis
 - Wavelet Analysis is a technique that uses different windows size adapted to the different spectral bands. This feature gives high frequency resolution in the low-bands and low frequency resolution in the high bands, the contrary occurs to the time resolution low for low-bands and high for high-bands as it is the nature of the Fast Fourier Transform. This feature is really positive for vocalizations as they tend to be fast in high-bands and slow for low-bands.
These characteristics of the WA can be used to denoise signals efficiently [Ramesh Babu, 2011].
- Wiener Filter in Frequency Domain

- Wiener Filter technique has already been used in other signal enhancement methods. The main idea of the Wiener Filter is to improve signal quality by adding noise to the same signal. An optimal filter for the noise signal is estimated by minimizing the Mean Square Error between the clean signal that is wanted and the estimated signal. This wanted signal which is clean has to be somehow estimated and this is done with two parameters the power spectral density and the noise previous to the filtering step. The problem of this technic is that it has a fixed frequency response at all frequencies [Chen et al., 2006].

The previous techniques for animal vocalization enhancement were tested with 3 species in [Ramesh Babu, 2011], the African Elephant, the Beluga whale and the Ortolan bunting. For Lemur vocalization the most interesting results are the ones obtained from the Elephant and the Beluga as they are both mammals although they have some differents in the body shape.

The filters were tested alone and combined, the result of combining them was really unsuccessful decreasing the power of each filter alone, only Kalman Filter piped with a Wiener Filter provided acceptable results. Standalone the filters worked better and Kalman Filter provided the best results with a significant difference.

2.4 Synthesis Techniques

2.4.1 Animal Vocalization Synthesis using HMM

Different techniques have been used for animal vocalization synthesis, the most recent ones have been Spectral Modeling Synthesis in [Dhar et al., 2010], Physical Modeling in [Kahrs and Avanzini, 2001] and less scientific approaches in Pure Data for example in [Martino, 2000]. In this thesis a Hidden Markov Model approach is meant to be implemented as recent research has demonstrated that HMM is succesful with speech synthesis, here a human speech Synthesis based in HMM from [Tokuda et al., 2013] is described in order to show how the system could work with Lemur vocalizations.

Speech Production

HMM for itself does not produce sound that is why it needs to base the synthesis in some method. In the actual method the source-filter technique is used to synthesize the sound. The source-filter method divides the signal between the excitation,

that may be white noise or a train of pulses (generated by the vocal chords) and the filtering, which simulates the vocal tract function. If we define the parameters there is the voicing information, the fundamental frequency and the spectral envelope. In the present model HMM predict these two parts by outputting two feature vectors. As the method has been explained in 2.3.1 the inside of HMM's will not be extended here.

Training and Synthesis

In the present method the Baum-Welch algorithm is used to estimate the maximum-likelihood of the HMM parameters. These parameters are formed by the source and the filter as it has been mentioned above, contrary to many methods which just use the filter, so the spectral part.

The problem of modeling both parts is that the source is not continuous, there are some points in vocalizations that there are silence and these means that the system can not output any values. For that the proposed solution is to use a continuous distribution for voiced frames and a discrete distribution for unvoiced frames, these spaces are switched according to the actual situation of the signal.

Both parts are modeled simultaneously by different streams in a multistream model.

To control utterances duration a semi-Markov structure is used, in this approach

the temporal structure is approximated by a Gaussian distribution.

As vocalizations are quite complex in terms of context and combination state tying is applied as a simplification technique. The idea is to cluster similar states that join model parameters to make the model more robust. This method is implemented using a hierarchical tree structure. Spectral filter, excitation and duration parameters are clustered in different trees which share the same stream of decisions.

After this process a set of labels containing vocalizations in its context are input to the model in order to synthesize the output of the system.

Characteristics of the approach

HMM based approaches have the advantage to provide great flexibility in modeling voice changes, like emotions, speaking styles and voice characteristics.

This method can adapt models with just a few samples if a similar model already exists, maximum-likelihood linear regression (MLLR) is used. This adaptation maps Gaussian probability density functions (pdfs) of the existing model into

the new model, this operation gives a functional adaptation of data.

Another characteristic of the present method is to interpolate models, if different models have been created there is the possibility to generate a new target model by interpolating the different HMM sets. This interpolation creates new voices containing mixtures of characteristics of the different models. With this technique generation of new speaking styles and dialects is possible without the data.

The good thing about this method is that models are created with data, this means that we can input new data to the system and it will output new HMM which will be able to generate the vocalizations provided by the data. This is particularly useful for Lemur vocalization generation, when the system is created it just needs datasets to create new species vocalization systems.

2.4.2 Open Source Tools

There are different available tools to implement HMM-based speech synthesis the most populars are HTS (which is a modification of HTK) and Festival Speech Synthesis System. HTS will be commented as it seems to be the most appropriate for the task.

HTS is a standalone toolkit that enables all the characteristics described above and also has the possibility to be used as a C library as it is just using standard C library. HTS has been developed by a group of volunteers from the Nagoya Institute of Technology.

Chapter 3

METHODOLOGY

After understanding and acknowledging the state of the art related to animal vocalizations analysis and synthesis it is time to start developing it. Our hypothesis is that it is possible to match the current technology in speech recognition and synthesis to the animal domain. In the following sections the methodology that has been followed will be presented in order to understand the whole work.

First the issues related to animal voices data will be explained, following it the process that is used to model and synthesize the voices will be defined in a theoretical way and finally an insight to the system is presented. To start a brief description of this thesis is presented along with the motivations that brought us to start this project.

3.1 Motivation

For starting we think that we must establish the reasons to start such a huge project in a Master Thesis and to explain the reasons why we want to use the technology that we have used.

The goal for this thesis is to achieve the basis for a system intended to synthesize Lemur vocalizations, departing from databases for training and using as target animal "phrases", it could be like a Text To Speech (TTS) system applied to animals (of course animals do not have proper "text").

As anyone into the music technology field can deduce this is a challenging project which requires transversal knowledge (ethologics, linguistics and music technology at least). For the modeling and synthesis part we want to use Hidden Markov Models (HMM).

The question is why are we doing this if we could just use samples or just copy vocal features and synthesize them. The main reason is the limitations that provide other techniques, if we use samples we can create new sounds, but they will always be the original sounds cut or transformed. If it is a single vocalization then there is no problem, but if we want to make a complex vocalizations formed by more than one vocalization then we can just concatenate and this process will lose naturality clearly. The same would happen if we synthesize it using features extracted from the vocalization that we want to emulate, for example with Matlab or straight with Python.

The other reason is the freedom that provides a TTS system, we just need to provide a text description of the sounds that have to be synthesized and if we have enough training data and a good phonetic definition the "phrase" is synthesized easily using HMM. Of course the results need to be improved, as human TTS systems are still in development process, applying them to animals needs still more work.

For creating our system we want to use HMM-based speech synthesis system (HTS) which is a plugin for Hidden Markov Model Toolkit - Speech Recognition toolkit (HTK). These tools are widely used in our research domain, the documentation is not really extense but there are forums, mail discussions and useful information available. It has been thought that this tool is complete enough and can fulfill our requirements.

The last reason is that HTS provides some methods to vary the output of the system in order to create users easily. There are different ways, but for example if a huge dataset from a single individual is modeled we can use just a few data from other individuals to interpolate their voices, change their emotivity and in conclusion alter the synthesized voice. This last feature is really useful in order to create slight variations with not much effort.

Now that the reasons for the thesis have been defined it is time to focus on the methodology.

3.2 Training Data

In this section the training data and its acquiring process is commented, it has been a breakpoint so we feel it must be explained clearly here in order to understand the further steps in the methodology.

3.2.1 Lemurs Dataset

At the beginning of this project we contacted Doctor Marco Gamba from University of Torino (Italy). He is a well known researcher in the field of ethology, which is the science in charge of explaining the behaviour of animals. Dr. Gamba has dedicated his career to study the behaviour of different Lemur species (Lemurs are primitive primates which are endemic to the country and island of Madagascar), a great part of his work is focused in Lemur communication. His work describes different species vocalizations and tries to define them in deepness covering "technological" aspects like fundamental frequency, formants, source of vocalization... (see figure 3.1). This aspect is really useful for the work that is done in this thesis.

We were expecting a lemur vocalization dataset along with information related

Mean and standard deviation of the acoustic parameters per vocal type. Number of average individual values considered is reported after the vocal type (N). Parameters we measured were: duration (DUR), average fundamental frequency (MeF0), minimum fundamental frequency (MiF0), maximum fundamental frequency (MaF0), standard deviation of the fundamental frequency (SdF0), cumulative variation of the fundamental frequency (SV), average first formant (F1), second formant (F2), third formant (F3), fourth formant (F4).

Vocalization	MeF0 (Hz)	MiF0 (Hz)	MaF0 (Hz)	SdF0 (Hz)	SV (Hz)
Long Grunt (5)	62±3	42±2	89±4	13±2	8±4
Long Grunt Clear Call (15)	61±5	46±4	84±7	10±1	12±3
Grunted Hoot (16)	69±3	53±3	88±5	11±2	22±3
Grunt (22)	57±4	49±5	66±4	5±1	11±3
Snort (4)	234±194	107±44	398±423	97±127	147±189
Click (9)	102±6	91±7	114±12	8±5	16±9
Hoot (9)	239±52	183±54	295±41	38±10	72±18
Alarm Call (11)	245±90	144±50	358±138	68±34	69±21
Tonal Call (6)	928±103	747±134	1017±87	74±27	127±44
Scream (14)	3773±884	2064±566	5352±841	1053±164	769±379

Vocalization	DUR (sec)	F1 (Hz)	F2 (Hz)	F3 (Hz)	F4 (Hz)
Long Grunt (5)	0.842±0.136	697±246	2720±458	4804±658	7068±609
Long Grunt Clear Call (15)	0.432±0.053	1184±181	2816±153	4560±246	6784±271
Grunted Hoot (16)	0.169±0.049	394±68	2509±114	4186±121	6500±274
Grunt (22)	0.134±0.045	489±131	2907±207	4519±241	6662±437
Snort (4)	0.304±0.067	866±457	3066±258	4973±366	7570±181
Click (9)	0.090±0.044	777±327	2663±282	4747±301	6794±318
Hoot (9)	0.214±0.064	516±82	2065±354	4455±312	6800±247
Alarm Call (11)	0.502±0.121	1286±373	3261±452	5700±404	8710±408
Tonal Call (6)	0.426±0.074	1148±93	2598±273	4600±386	6917±434
Scream (14)	0.465±0.147	3001±677	7692±798	13351±1016	16967±987

Figure 3.1: Example of a table showing different call features from [Gamba and Giacoma, 2007].

to the vocalizations. The information had to solve us some doubts about animal vocalizations in general and how they can match (or at least try) human vocalizations. The problem appeared at the end of the term were we discovered that the sharing of data and information was becoming more difficult than expected. The process entered into bureaucratic domains and agreements between universities which is a tedious and slow work. At the beginning of summer it was still unclear if we would get the data or not so we tried other options.

The first option was to search for other datasets of lemur vocalizations, changing the species was not useful because we had been studying and reading about lemurs during the whole year and this work shall not be lost or be disused. After searching in deepness through the internet it became clear that it was impossible to find a dataset that suited our thesis. We find a really good dataset from "Museum für Naturkunde Berlin" in the "Tierstimmen archiv", it was really well anotated but the unsolvable problem were the recordings. They contained lots of background noise (bird singings, other animals vocalizations...) as they were recorded in the wild and the recordings also contained many lemur individuals speaking at the same time or similar disturbances. This dataset was not fit for our work so we searched for other datasets.

After a long time searching for other datasets just one useful dataset appeared. It was a dataset from Wikipedia containing Lemur Catta vocalizations. The recordings were really nice and contained different single vocalizations from just one individual. It was perfect for our purposes but the handicap was that there were only one or two (three or four at the most) samples for each vocalizations, thing that made this dataset useless for training.

After all this disappointment we decided to continue with a new strategy that is explained in the following section.

3.2.2 Recording Animal Vocalizations

As we did not have prerecorded sounds the solution was to record them. As extracting good quality recordings from animals is a complex task, apart from the handicap that Lemurs exist only in Madagascar and recording in a Zoo would be an even more complex task, we decided to record our own animals.

The idea was to record a human individual trying to emulate the Lemur vocalizations that we had from the Wikipedia dataset. At first glance it may have no sense to use human recordings, but for the system that we aim to implement it is really useful. The human recordings would not be the same as the Lemur vocalizations, but they will share some features, entonation and dynamics that would make them appropriate for our goals. As we need to make the basis of the system starting from some recordings that seem like animals is enough.

To create this dataset we chose 4 vocals from the Lemur Catta dataset which were Moans, Early High Wails, Huhs and Purrs. The chosen vocalizations were the ones that a human voice could fit better plus the Purr which was a roaring vocalization that would give some clues for synthesizing characteristic animal voices. The created dataset is formed by 228 samples containing a single vocalization each one, there are 46 Purrs, 72 Moans, 48 Early High Wails and 62 Huhs. All the samples were recorded in an isolated room using a mic Sennheiser E914, with a Moto UltraLite-mk3 Hybrid soundcard and using Qbase as a recording software, the sample rate was 44.1 KHz and the format chosen was raw *wav*. All the vocalizations were done in the same place and same conditions all uttered by the same individual which is the author of this thesis.

3.3 HMM based synthesis

In the latest years Hidden Markov Models (HMM) have become the most popular tool in Automatic Speech Recognition (ASR), although HMM have extended their presence in other fields that can be modeled as stochastic processes [Carrillo Aguilar, 2007]. With the same technique used for modeling and recognition we can synthesize speech by generating waveforms that reproduce the features extracted before. This system is a Text-to-speech (TTS) synthesis technique and its main advantage is the flexibility in varying speech characteristics like emotion, style or the identity [Tokuda et al., 2013].

The HMM based synthesis approach uses several annotated training data which is modeled by a time-series stochastic generative model. HMMs represent the phoneme sequences along with linguistic contexts, this model drives a vocoder that controls the excitation parameters along with the vocal tract parameters. In 2012 76% of the papers presented at Interspeech 2012 used HMM based approaches thing that makes HMM based synthesis a really popular technique in the state of the art. Following this brief description the process is described in details.

Sound Generation

As it is known by everyone it is possible to emulate the human speech production by using the source filter model. Briefly there is a source which is represented by white noise normally or a train of impulses. This signal is then filtered by a digital resonant filter which emulates the glottal flow, the vocal tract resonance, the

lip radiation and other less important features. This source filter model includes voicing information, fundamental frequency and the spectral envelope (which can contain different attributes mel-cepstral coefficients, line-spectral pairs...). With this parameters is possible to make an acceptable reconstruction of the speech waveform.

HMMs are used to predict the parameters for the source-filter model from the text that has to be synthesized. This is done through observation vectors that are formed at each frame by concatenating spectral and excitation parameters.

Hidden Markov Model

Every N-state HMM characterizes an utterance and it is characterized by a set of initial-state probabilities $\{\pi_i\}_{i=1}^N$, state-transition probabilities $\{a_{ij}\}_{i,j=1}^N$ and state-output probability distributions (which are typically single multivariate Gaussian distributions) $\{b_i(\circ)\}_{i=1}^N$.

We just need μ_i as a d-by-1 mean vector, Σ_i as a d-by-d covariance matrix, d is the dimension of the acoustic parameters and \mathbf{o}_t is an observation vector which contains the acoustic parameters at frame t . With all this parameters we can define an N-state HMM λ as

$$b_i(\mathbf{o}_t) = N(\mathbf{o}_t; \mu_i, \Sigma_i) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{(2\pi)^d |\Sigma_i|}} \exp\left\{ -\frac{1}{2} (\mathbf{o}_t - \mu_i)^T \Sigma_i^{-1} (\mathbf{o}_t - \mu_i) \right\}$$

The training of HMMs and synthesis from HMMs are simply described with the following equations. Where $\mathbf{O} = [\mathbf{O}_1^T, \mathbf{O}_2^T, \dots, \mathbf{O}_T^T]^T$ and W are a set of speech parameters and corresponding linguistic specifications that are used for the training of HMMs. $\mathbf{o} = [\mathbf{o}_1^T, \mathbf{o}_2^T, \dots, \mathbf{o}_T^T]^T$ and w are the speech parameters and linguistic specifications that we need to synthesize, we just need to know that $\mathbf{q} = \{q_1, q_2, \dots, q_T\}$ is a state sequence:

$$\text{Training} : \lambda_{max} = \operatorname{argmax}_{\lambda} p(\mathbf{O} | \lambda, W)$$

$$p(\mathbf{O} | \lambda, W) = \sum_{\forall \mathbf{q}} \pi_{q_0} \prod_{t=1}^T a_{q_{t-1} q_t} b_{q_t}(\mathbf{O}_t)$$

$$\text{Synthesis} : \mathbf{o}_{max} = \operatorname{argmax}_{\mathbf{o}} p(\mathbf{o} | \lambda_{max}, w)$$

Speech Parameter Generation from HMM

The idea of this algorithm is quite simple, given a set of HMMs and a text to be synthesized the most probable speech parameter vector sequence will be output. This is done by using state-duration probability distributions. But if we use just this process we lose realism because there is a conditional independence of state-output probabilities and that provokes that the the mean vectors (speech parameters) are being generated step-wise, and the result is unnatural.

To understand better the concept of the algorithm we can see an example of generated speech parameters from a sentence-level HMM composed by concatenating two phoneme-level HMMs in figure 3.2.

Figure 3.2: Example of statistics and generated speech parameters for phonemes /a/ and /i/ from [Tokuda et al., 2013].

In the figure we can see the trajectory of the 0th mel-cepstral coefficient $c(0)$ in the generated speech parameters along with its dynamic features. The dotted vertical lines represent a state output. The shaded zones along with the dashed lines in it represent the standard deviation of the state and the state mean respectively. The three trajectories are determined by maximizing their output probabilities. The result is that the trajectories are realistic due to the constraints extracted from the dynamic and static feature statistics.

Training

The main idea in the training step is to use the Baum-Welch algorithm to get the maximum likelihood estimation of the HMM parameters. To achieve that HMMs need to model spectral parameters and excitation parameters at the same time in order to drive the source-filter synthesizer. This is not trivial because we need to apply the conventional discrete and the continuous HMMs to F_0 pattern modeling, but F_0 values are not always present i.e. in the unvoiced regions. To solve this problem the current technique uses multispace probability distributions (MPD) for modeling this situations. A typical MPD for solving the previous example would have two parts, a continuous distribution for the voiced frames and a discrete distribution for the unvoiced frames.

This would solve the problem of discontinuities in F_0 values, but to keep excitation and spectral parameters synchronized the two types are modeled simultaneously by separate streams in a multistream HMM. This technique uses different state output probability distributions for modeling individual parts of the observation vector.

Another important feature present in the training is the temporal structure of the vocalizations. Each HMM has its state-duration probability distribution to model this feature. The simplest way to control this would be to add a logic duration probability that would exponentially decrease with the increase of duration but the result is not realistic. The solution that proposes this method is to use a semi-Markov structure where the temporal structure is approximated by a Gaussian distribution.

The last important feature that incorporates this method is context dependency, defining it linguistic specifications are taken into account. In HMM based speech synthesis phoneme information is used as in other methods, the novelty is to extend this data with more linguistic contexts like lexical stress, tone, part-of-speech information and pitch accent for the context dependent modeling of HMMs. The reason is that prosodic and duration parameters could be affected by minor segments linguistic information. When we enter such a small domain the information that we need grows a lot, this means that we need several training data in order to extract the needed information, and this volume becomes too big. The proposed solution is to apply state tying techniques, the idea is to cluster similar states and to tie model parameters among several context-dependent HMMs in order to improve the system robustness. This process is conducted in a hierarchical tree

structure manner and the tree size is determined based on a criterion called minimum description length. Spectral, excitation and duration parameters do not share context dependency, so they are clustered separately by using stream-dependent decision trees.

Synthesis

The last process in the system is the synthesis. First the text that has to be synthesized is converted into a sequence of context-dependent labels, according to these labels a sentence-level HMM is built by concatenating context-dependent HMMs. Each state duration is determined by maximizing the probability based on the state duration probability distribution. After that the speech parameter generation algorithm is used to maximise the sequence of speech parameters output probability, this includes excitation and spectral parameters. To end the process speech waveforms are resynthesized straight from the generated spectral and excitation parameters by using a speech synthesis filter.

3.4 HMM-based Speech Synthesis System (HTS)

The main problem when we are talking about synthesizing speech is the data. For our purposes we need to train the system with a huge amount of data to extract all the features that we have mentioned before. We need an optimal computing tool to overcome this problem. Here is where HTS appears.

HTS is a plugin for the HTK toolbox which was developed at Nagoya Institute of technology by Dr. Tokuda et al. [Tokuda et al., 2002].

HTS has a flexible architecture, it is composed by a set of library modules which are called by the different available tools according to their function. The tools are used as commands which can be parametrized by different options. In general, capital letter options mean global parameters, like $-C$ which defines the configuration file, while minuscule letter options mean value options where the parameter is redefined [Carrillo Aguilar, 2007].

The most important libraries for HTS are:

- HAudio: it controls the acquiring of live audio signals.

- HAdapt: adapts the recognizer to one or more individuals.
- HLabel: manages label files.
- HMath: manages high level structures like matrices or vectors.
- HMem: manages memory at low level.
- HModel: interprets HMM definitions.
- HSigP: applies signal processing operations.
- HUtil: routines for manipulating HMM.
- HWave: manages input and output files.

We will not enter into the deepness of HTS, what have been done in this Thesis is applying a HTS complex demo for japanese into Lemur vocalizations. In the following section the followed process and the modified system is explained in order to understand the work done.

3.4.1 System adaptation to animal vocalizations

The schema that follows the system is like the one in figure 3.3.

In the following sections the schema is defined by parts and the commands used at each part of the process are explained:

Data Preparation and Features Extraction

The first step for the system is to prepare the data and configure the initial variables.

In our case we input the sound as raw files each one containing a single vocalization, this data has to be anotated in order to extract the HMMs. Each sound file has two label files one for the full-context and one for the monophone context.

Figure 3.3: HMM-based speech synthesis system from [Tokuda et al., 2002].

Here we can see an example of a label file:

```
0000000 2883446 sil
2883446 12911111 moa
12911111 15511111 sil
```

A single phoneme is used because we want to model the whole vocalization, it would be difficult to add phoneme-level description because two reasons: the first one is the difference between animal vocalization and humans, in human speech it has a sense to model the phonemes that are repeated in several words but in animal vocalizations we are just interested in the whole vocalizations were the sense relies not in smaller units of production [ten Cate and Okanoya, 2012]; the second reason is more practical and is the naturality of the used dataset, as the sound files are human recordings they do have excessive variation in order to define proper smaller units of production that add some sense to the training.

When all the data labels and sound files are ready the system is configured in order to adapt the parameters to the desired work. Apart from defining the path to the needed tools which are HTS, Speech Signal Processing Toolkit (SPTK) and HTS-engine there are a few other variables that must be adapted to our purpose, the main ones are the following:

- *FULLCONTEXT_FORMAT* - label format
- *DATASET* - dataset name (prefix for the training files)
- *SPEAKER* - speaker name (2nd prefix for the training files)
- *FRAMELEN* - frame length in point
- *FRAMESHIFT* - frame shift in point
- *WINDOWTYPE* - window type: Blackman, Hamming or Hanning
- *FFTLLEN* - FFT length in point
- *SAMPFREQ* - sampling frequency in Hz
- *MGCORDER* - order of Mel-generalized Cepstrum (MGC) analysis
- *LOWERF0* - lower limit for the F_0 values in Hz
- *UPPERF0* - higher limit for the F_0 values in Hz

For our system we used just varied a few parameters because all the default values are adapted to human speech, and our vocalizations recordings were from human source.

SAMPFREQ = 44100

HIGHERF0 = 700

DATASET = *Lemurs*

SPEAKER = *m001*

WINDOWSIZE = 13000.0 (*in 100ns units*)

Once all is configured the first step of the system is to extract all the features according to the label files provided. Excitation (F_0) and Spectral data (*MGC*) are extracted at this point, Label files are gathered into Master Label Files (MLF),

also all the necessary files list are created in this step. After this process all the data to start the training is present.

Training

In this section the training process is described and the main commands and options are explained, some intersteps and trivial processes are avoided to clear the explanation.

At the beginning HMMs are presented as void templates that have to be filled they contain Stream information, State definitions (containing mean, variance and GConst, which gives the part of the log probability of a Gaussian that can be precomputed [Young et al., 2006]) and the transition matrix. To start *HCompV* (commands start with H and will be formatted like this ones) computes an average model for every HMM along with the variance floors, this step is done in order to create a flat start were all the states from the models are equal.

The first proper step is done with *HInit* which initializes the models using the training data gathered in the previous step. The system iterates until it converges to a non advancing point. Following it the resulting data is treated through *HRest* which uses the Baum-Welch algorithm with a set of observation sequences to re-estimate the paramteres for a single HMM.

The following step is to create a monophone Master Macro File (MMF) by using *HHEd*. This command operates with the stream weights and the duration paramteres to create one MMF for each one.

After *HERest* re-estimates the parameters of a set of HMMs by using an embedded training version of the Baum-Welch algorithm.

HHEd is used again to copy the gathered monophone MMF to a fullcontext one containing the superior level of utterances. The same process applied to monophones is applied to the fullcontext training files. Once this is done *HHEd* is called again in order to cluster the tree-based context. Here context similarities are gathered together and the decision trees related to it are pruned according to the training data.

Before generating speech parameters *HSMMAlign* forces the alignment of the no-silent Global Variances (GV) by using Hidden Semi Markov Models.

The last process before the synthesis is done by *HMGenS*, which generates speech parameter trajectories that maximise their output probabilities for a given sentence of HMMs [Zen et al., 2006]. The same process is done by using HTS-engine.

Now all the information to generate the waveforms is ready and we enter the syn-

thesis part.

Synthesis

The synthesis is quite straightforward as we already have the sequence of context-dependent labels that are the target, the maximizations of the duration probabilities and the spectral and excitation parameters. The SPTK is used to generate the final speech waveform directly from the excitation and spectral parameters by using the mel-log spectral approximation filter (MLSA). The process is done with 1 and 2 mixes, with HTS-engine and with semi-tied covariance matrix although in my case the four options give identical results.

One raw audio file is output for each sentence that has to be generated.

Chapter 4

EVALUATION AND RESULTS

In this chapter the results extracted along with the system performance are evaluated in order to extract some further conclusions.

4.1 Vocalizations Evaluation

An intuitive way to evaluate correctly the synthesized vocalizations would be to use subjective tests asking individuals about the degree of similarity between the original, the human recorded and the synthesized samples. After having heard the three versions of the audio we can state that the samples are clearly differentiated and the information that would be extracted by using subjective tests would be logical and would not bring anything to the current work. This situation was expected because the HMM-based synthesis still has room for improving the techniques, and the state of the art of synthesized speech still sounds like a vocoder and there is no doubt in differentiating original samples from the generated ones. The second point is that dynamics are much more important in animal vocalizations as they carry great parts of information and HTS is still improving this factors.

So having into account the previous premises the results are evaluated by comparing the various signals in the temporal domain along with the comparison of different audio features that give the clue of the reasons of the variation. This analysis could be done automatically, but as it has been a manual tuning process with a few results (in quantity) we thought that it might give more information to make an individual analysis to each sample and to its ancestors than to make a batch processing analysis.

As it has been mentioned before this thesis is focused in 4 Lemur vocaliza-

tions which are *Moan*, *Huhs*, *Early High Wails* and *Purr*. The last one, the *Purr* is different from the others because it is a modulated roaring sound, The other three are quite similar as they are tonal calls with different durations and entonations.

4.1.1 Early High Wails

Temporal Domain

The Early High Wails have the most tonal variations and are the longest.

The original signal is divided in three parts (figure 4.1), a first one with a slow and deep attack, a middle part with energy variation and a final start that keeps stable until it ends quite fast. In the human recordings (figure 4.2) the signal is smoother and the attack gets faster, the second region is extended covering almost the first region, the last region is longer and rises in energy until almost the end were ends smoothly.

The synthesized version (figure 4.3) is like an envelope for the recorded version with some variations, the attack is really long and smooth, the variations in energy are really smooth and defined. The final region is shortened and just ends softly.

In terms of energy variance (figure 4.5) the synthesized and the recorded versions are really similar, one is a simplification of the other. The problem is that the time moments of variance are not kept, and the regions are shortened in the synthesized version, this is due to the low expressivity of the vocoder and to the variations in the training recordings. Also the original signal has a variance that could not be kept in the human recordings.

With the Zero Crossing Rate (figure 4.10) we can extract few conclusions as the difference is not really high. The synthesized sample has the highest rate so it may have more higher frequency content.

Spectral Features

Early High Wails are the most tonal vocalizations along with *Moans*, so a greater variation in the spectrum is expected, spectral flux mean, spectral roll off mean and spectral centroid mean are examined in this section.

From the Spectral Centroid (figure 4.7) we can not extract that much information, just that the recorded version lost the tone, but the synthesized version keeps

Figure 4.1: The original Vocalization.

Figure 4.2: The recorded vocalization.

Figure 4.3: The synthesized vocalization.

Figure 4.4: Plots of the 3 different *Early High Wail* signals with its envelope on top.

quite close to the recorded. It seems that the F_0 was caught by HTS with quite precision.

From the RollOff (at 85% of the energy) (figure 4.8) we can state that the synthesized version has a lot more harmonicity than the recorded, it is a difference of 2000Hz so it is quite considerable.

The Spectral Flux of the original Lemur version is high so it means that the call is rich in different tones and variations. These spectral variance was not reflected in the recordings so it got lost before the system. The mean variation between the

Figure 4.5: Plot of the energy variation in the 3 different vocalizations.

Figure 4.6: Plot of the Zero Crossing Rate in the 3 different vocalizations.

recorded and the synthesized version, so in this part the system worked well.

Figure 4.7: The original vocalization.

Figure 4.8: The recorded vocalization.

Figure 4.9: Spectral Centroid mean and Spectral Roll Off mean for the *Early High Wails* samples.

4.1.2 Huhs

Temporal Domain

The Huhs are the shortest calls although they contain tonal variation.

The original signal (figure 4.11) is a really short call with two clear regions, the first part has a smooth and low attack which is followed by a peak of energy ending abruptly. The recorded version (figure 4.12) could not keep this dynamics so clear, it has a steeper attack which rises and lows a bit. The following region makes a little rise in energy and then descends linearly.

Figure 4.10: Plot of the Spectral Flux mean in the 3 different vocalizations.

The synthesized sample (figure 4.13) is really different in terms of dynamics and regions, it just have one single region which has a smooth attack with a smooth release, no high amplitude spikes.

The energy variance is really different in this call, as it is a really short call HTS could not caught all the variations. The recorded and the original version have similarities but the variance in the synthesis is almost null. We can see it clearly in the figure 4.15 and in the amplitude envelopes above (figure 4.14).

The Zero Crossing Rate (ZCR)(figure 4.16) gives us some clues that could match the mean frequency. The original frequency has a really low ZCR as it is a tonal sound with hard low frequency presence. The recorded sample tries to emulate but it has a higher ZCR. The synthesized sample loses trace and doubles the recorded ZCR this means that it has higher frequency component and that the sound is not as tonal as it should be.

Spectral Features

Huhs are really short calls, so the output of the system could match the tone and became similar to the recorded one. As in the other sections spectral flux mean, spectral roll off mean and spectral centroid mean are examined.

The Spectral Centroid (figure 4.17) does not give too much information alone as in the previous case. The result is similar, the recorded version lifted the spec-

Figure 4.11: The original Vocalization.

Figure 4.12: The recorded vocalization.

Figure 4.13: The synthesized vocalization.

Figure 4.14: Plots of the 3 different *Huhs* signals with its envelope on top.

tral centroid, and the synthesized version is close but still has a higher Centroid. The roll off (figure 4.18) for the synthesized version is the highest even above 7KHz, it lost trace of the recorded version as its roll off is 3000Hz lower. It seems that the system is adding too much harmonicity to the vocalizations.

As it is a short call, the spectral flux mean (figure 4.20) is lower than the previous, but still the synthesized version is far much lower than even the recorded version. The variations in the tonality are completely lost in the synthesis, maybe due to the short duration of the call.

Figure 4.15: Plot of the energy variation in the 3 different vocalizations.

Figure 4.16: Plot of the Zero Crossing Rate in the 3 different vocalizations.

4.1.3 Moan

Temporal Domain

Moans are really similar to *Early High Wails*, tonal and long but with less variation in the tone.

Figure 4.17: The original vocalization.

Figure 4.18: The recorded vocalization.

Figure 4.19: Spectral Centroid mean and Spectral Roll Off mean for the *Huhs* samples.

The original signal (figure 4.21) is really smooth it has a long steep attack at the very beginning but rising smoothly with an even smoother end. The recorded version (figure 4.22) is quite similar, the attack at the beginning is much more slower while the release is a bit steeper, in the middle some little energy variations appear.

The energy variance (figure 4.25) is logical, in the sense that the original has the most variance (although is not really higher) while the recorded has the half

Figure 4.20: Plot of the Spectral Flux for the 3 vocalizations.

of the variance. The synthesized version is still with no variance, so it seems that HTS is not catching the dynamics in the vocals.

The Zero Crossing Rate (ZCR)(figure 4.26) is equal to the *Huhs* so we might extract conclusions from this feature supported by the other features.

Spectral Features

Moan are really quite similar to *Early High Wails* so we expect to get similar results in the spectral domain, although the tonal variation in the present vocal is not as pronounced as in the mentioned.

The Spectral Centroid (figure 4.27) for the synthesized and the recorded is really close thing that is positive, the system worked in this case.

Contrary to the Centroid the Roll Off (figure 4.28) splits the synthesized with the recorded and original versions, the synthesized has a really high roll off (above 4500Hz) while the recorded and the original values are below 1500Hz.

The Spectral Flux (figure 4.30) behaves like in the other vocalizations, the synthesized versions are losing all the spectral flux so they lose the tone variance.

Figure 4.21: The original Vocalization.

Figure 4.22: The recorded vocalization.

Figure 4.23: The synthesized vocalization.

Figure 4.24: Plots of the 3 different *Moan* signals with its envelope on top.

4.1.4 Purr

Temporal Domain

Purrs are the most different vocalizations as they are low roarings with a considerable amount of modulation.

The original signal (figure 4.31) has nothing to do with the others. The recorded version (figure 4.32) has 3 clear parts, the first one with a steep attack and a really smooth and long release, the middle part is like the first part but

Figure 4.25: Plot of the energy variation in the 3 different vocalizations.

Figure 4.26: Plot of the Zero Crossing Rate in the 3 different vocalizations.

much more shorter and quicker and the last part is an smooth vocalizations with a quiet attack and release.

The synthesized version (figure 4.33) is similar in shape to the recorded signal but it has high frequency variations that can be observed due to the filter used for computing the envelope, which was 2nd order butterworth. The middle part is

Figure 4.27: The original vocalization.

Figure 4.28: The recorded vocalization.

Figure 4.29: Spectral Centroid mean and Spectral Roll Off mean for the *Moan* samples.

also lost in the synthesized along with the modulation that contained the recorded sample.

The energy variance (figure 4.35) is really low in this call, even in the original sample. Anyway the recorded and synthesized vocalizations have almost the same value, which is positive, but it is almost null.

Figure 4.30: Plot of the Spectral Flux for the 3 vocalizations.

Spectral Features

Purr do not have that much tonal component but have modulations which are present in the spectral domain, due to the handicaps of HTS it is difficult to catch this few variations.

The Spectral Centroid (figure 4.36) for the synthesized and the recorded is quite close, while the centroid for the original is far much lower. As it is a different vocalization it breaks the stability that the Spectral Roll Off (figure 4.37) had in the previous vocalizations. In this case the recorded one has the highest value due to the roaring, the synthesized value is still high, and the original presents the highest value.

The Spectral Flux (figure 4.39) is even more clear in this vocalization because the recorded and the synthesized have almost the same value, which is really low, while the original keeps a great variation in the spectrum. It seems that spectral variations are complicated for our system.

Figure 4.31: The original Vocalization.

Figure 4.32: The recorded vocalization.

Figure 4.33: The synthesized vocalization.

Figure 4.34: Plots of the 3 different *Purr* signals with its envelope on top.

Figure 4.35: Plot of the energy variation in the 3 different vocalizations.

Figure 4.36: The original vocalization.

Figure 4.37: The recorded vocalization.

Figure 4.38: Spectral Centroid mean and Spectral Roll Off mean for the *Purr* samples.

Figure 4.39: Plot of the Spectral Flux for the 3 vocalizations.

4.2 System Evaluation

After evaluating each vocalization some conclusions can be extracted but first a technical evaluation is presented.

The system created with HTS is quite complex it requires to understand how it works at a phonetics level which is hard from the point of view of a sound designer. The parameters that can be touched are varied and after experimenting and reading, the ones with best performance have been chosen an even in this way the results are not the best.

The label files have also been tested in different modes, phonemes, words and phrases. In the phoneme mode is impossible to extract each phoneme separately due to the language specifications the system gets confused and understands different sounds for the labels. At words level is the best option because the system recognises the whole word as a phoneme and models it, the model is not really precise but as it has been presented in the previous section is not awesomely bad. At sentence level the system gets confused again because it mixes all the words it does not extract a clear model and mixes words that should not get mixed, the reason is another time the language specifications (they are presented in the following subsection).

The synthesized sounds have a clear vocoder sound which makes them awkward, if it is a human that is speaking in a vocoder is strange but it is understandable. In the lemur callings this is a problem, because all the sense falls on the dynamics, intonation and tone, this means that is really difficult to achieve an acceptable result with the experienced synthesis technique. Maybe it would be useful to try other synthesizers done for singing voices like *Sinsy* [Oura et al., 2010] or *Vocaloid* [Bonada and Serra, 2007]. For the results we obtained it could have sense to use one of this synthesizers to improve the quality of the generated sounds.

The other problematic spot is the dataset that has been used with the system, all the recordings are a single human voice, which surely makes it easier for the system to model it. This factor may have improved the quality of the synthesis because a real animal voices dataset would have change the paradigm for sure.

Phonetics and Language issues

HTS has a great offer in the domain of phonetics and language configuration and definition. Every language has its own rules that can be defined in the system, this is used for context clustering and state tying, the idea is to group contexts that are similar or phonemes that are pronounced in the same way. Even units smaller than a phoneme can be configured, they are called mora.

This factor has been a major problem for the our system. As Lemur vocalizations were used we needed much more information than we had or we could found to define some kind of basic rules for Lemur vocalizations at so low level. A kind of vocabulary was tried by defining at some low level how the vocalizations should sound or be pronounced. The result was worst than using the default dictionaries. This part should be improved with the collaboration of an ethology department or a person that controls pretty much the species vocalization.

In conclusion I would say that the goal of achieving a system for synthesizing animal vocalizations has been accomplished, the problem now resides in tuning the system and creating some phonetic rules specific to a species mainly.

Chapter 5

CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

The present work in this master thesis has focused on developing a system to achieve analysis and synthesis of animal vocalizations, precisely Lemur vocalizations. A toolbox called HTS has been used for that as it is ready for doing the same process in human vocalizations and most of mammals share the same phonatory system, thing that is an advantage. There is no system like the one that has been created in this work, as the other similar systems had a less scientific point of view or were only for leisure purposes. A new path for research has been opened as the system still needs further work in order to get a tool with a respectful level. But anyway the system has been achieved and the door is opened.

5.1 Contributions

The following list contains the main contributions of this work:

- Regarding the reviewed literature it has been stated that no serious system to synthesize animal vocalizations from datasets exist, so it is a virgin field in sound design that can be explored.
- HTS is a versatile system that can be used with any language, even animal vocalizations as its HMM-based synthesis technique is really powerful and still in development.
- A system for animal vocalizations analysis and synthesis has been created, it needs development but the system is functional at the moment.

- A review to the Lemur vocalizations literature has been done, although at the end it has not been used as it was expected the material is still there and can be used for further work.

5.2 Conclusions

Considering the motivations and goals presented in the introduction and having into account the above presented contributions, some conclusions can be obtained.

The system that has been created is working but it needs to be improved in order to satisfy the nowadays standards. As a research tool is useful because it has set a starting point that can be used, modified and improved. The results achieved have given clues on where are the weak points, which in terms of vocalizations are harmonic control, tonal variation, modulations and clear phoneme definitions.

Working in a project of such characteristics requires the aid of someone who controls animal vocalizations, by the simple fact that human speech has its own rules of pronunciation but translating them to animal vocalizations is not trivial. Concretely there is no direct translation and a "new" language has to be set in order to synthesize good samples. Without this help there is room for improve but it might be a tough way not available to everyone.

The last conclusion is that at the moment it has been proved that vocoders are not the best way to synthesize animal voices a different system should be tested in order to improve results.

A virgin domain of research has been open that has multiple applications, from videogame/movie sound design, to ethology studies passing through plague control using animal voices. The possibilities are great and the door is open for further research.

5.3 Future Work

As it has been mentioned a new field is open, here some of the further steps are presented:

- The first step could be to try the same system with a real dataset containing Lemurs (or mammals) vocalizations. This could revalidate the functionality of the system. It is a pity that this step could not have been fulfilled because

it could have expanded this work enormously. Anyway the work done is not in vain so it still has to be done.

- As it has been mentioned the synthesis is still not clearly satisfying, it should be test how the system works using a different synthesis engine. HTS can be combined with Sinsy, which is dedicated to singing voices, surely so it could be a first option to start.
- A deeper study about the chosen animal vocalizations should be done in order to improve the quality of the synthesis. Some basic rules about the relation between audio units (animal phonemes) and its context would help a lot to improve the system, but this is out of the sound design field.
- Other species of animals, different from mammals, could be tried in order to see which is the reaction of the system and if there is viability in using HTS in other domains more away from the typical source filter scheme.

Bibliography

- [Bonada and Serra, 2007] Bonada, J. and Serra, X. (2007). Synthesis of the singing voice by performance sampling and spectral models. *Signal Processing Magazine, IEEE*, 24(2):67–79.
- [Carrillo Aguilar, 2007] Carrillo Aguilar, R. (2007). DESIGN AND MANIPULATION OF HIDDEN MARKOV MODELS USING HTK TOOLS . A TUTORIAL. *Ingeniare*, 15(1):18–26.
- [Chen et al., 2006] Chen, J., Benesty, J., Huang, Y. A., and Doclo, S. (2006). New Insights Into the Noise Reduction Wiener Filter. *Ieee Transactions On Audio Speech And Language Processing*, 14(4):1218–1234.
- [Clemins and Johnson, 2006] Clemins, P. J. and Johnson, M. T. (2006). Generalized perceptual linear prediction features for animal vocalization analysis. *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, 120(1):527.
- [Clemins, Patrick J., S.B., 2005] Clemins, Patrick J., S.B., S. (2005). *Automatic Classification of Animal Vocalization*. PhD thesis, Marquette University, Milwaukee, Wisconsin.
- [Dave, 2013] Dave, N. (2013). Feature Extraction Methods LPC , PLP and MFCC In Speech Recognition. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL FOR ADVANCE RESEARCH IN ENGINEERING AND TECHNOLOGY*, 1(Vi):1–5.
- [Dhar et al., 2010] Dhar, P. K., Khan, M. I., Deb, K., and Kim, J.-m. (2010). A Modified Spectral Modeling Synthesis Algorithm for Whale Sound. *International Journal of Computer Science and Network Security*, 10(9):34–41.
- [Fant, 1981] Fant, G. (1981). The source filter concept in voice production(Quarterly Progress and Status Report). *STL-QPSR*, 1:21–37.
- [Faragó et al., 2014] Faragó, T., Andics, A., Devecseri, V., Kis, A., Gácsi, M., and Miklósi, A. (2014). Humans rely on the same rules to assess emotional valence and intensity in conspecific and dog vocalizations. *Biology letters*, 10(January).

- [Fitch, 2000] Fitch, W. T. (2000). The phonetic potential of nonhuman vocal tracts: comparative cineradiographic observations of vocalizing animals. *Phonetica*, 57(2-4):205–18.
- [Fitch, 2006] Fitch, W. T. (2006). Production of Vocalizations in Mammals. *Visual Communication*, 3(2006):145.
- [Fosler-lussier, 1998] Fosler-lussier, E. (1998). Markov Models and Hidden Markov Models: A Brief Tutorial. 1198(510).
- [Gamba et al., 2012] Gamba, M., Friard, O., and Giacoma, C. (2012). Vocal Tract Morphology Determines Species-Specific Features in Vocal Signals of Lemurs (Eulemur). *International Journal of Primatology*, 33(6):1453–1466.
- [Gamba and Giacoma, 2006] Gamba, M. and Giacoma, C. (2006). Vocal Tract Modeling in a Prosimian Primate : The Black and White Ruffed Lemur. *ACTA ACUSTICA UNITED WITH ACUSTICA*, 92:749–755.
- [Gamba and Giacoma, 2007] Gamba, M. and Giacoma, C. (2007). Quantitative acoustic analysis of the vocal repertoire of the crowned lemur. *Ethology Ecology & Evolution*, 19(4):323–343.
- [Gamba and Giacoma, 2010] Gamba, M. and Giacoma, C. (2010). Key issues in the study of primate acoustic signals, an update. *Journal of anthropological sciences = Rivista di antropologia : JASS / Istituto italiano di antropologia*, 88:215–20.
- [Hermansky, 1990] Hermansky, H. (1990). Perceptual linear predictive (PLP) analysis of speech. *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, 87(4):1738–1752.
- [Kahrs and Avanzini, 2001] Kahrs, M. and Avanzini, F. (2001). COMPUTER SYNTHESIS OF BIRD SONGS AND CALLS. In *COST G-6 Conference on Digital Audio Effects (DAFX-01)*, pages 3–7.
- [Maretti et al., 2010] Maretti, G., Sorrentino, V., Finomana, A., Gamba, M., and Giacoma, C. (2010). Not just a pretty song: an overview of the vocal repertoire of Indri indri. *Journal of anthropological sciences = Rivista di antropologia : JASS / Istituto italiano di antropologia*, 88:151–65.
- [Martino, 2000] Martino, R. (2000). *Synthesaurus : An Animal Vocalization Synthesizer*. PhD thesis, NorthWestern University.
- [Naish, 2010] Naish, D. (2010). Pouches, pockets and sacs in the heads, necks and chests of mammals, part I: primates.

- [Oura et al., 2010] Oura, K., Mase, A., Yamada, T., Muto, S., Nankaku, Y., and Tokuda, K. (2010). Recent development of the hmm-based singing voice synthesis system-sinsy. In *SSW*, pages 211–216.
- [Pereira et al., 1988] Pereira, M. E., Seeligson, M. L., and Macedonia, J. M. (1988). The behavioral repertoire of the black-and-white ruffed lemur, *Varecia variegata variegata* (Primates: Lemuridae). *Folia primatologica; international journal of primatology*, 51:1–32.
- [Rabiner and Schafer, 2007] Rabiner, L. R. and Schafer, R. W. (2007). *Introduction to Digital Speech Processing*, volume 1.
- [Ramesh Babu, 2011] Ramesh Babu, G. (2011). ENHANCEMENT OF ANIMAL VOCALIZATION USING VARIOUS ALGORITHMS. *International Journal of Engineering Science and Technology (IJEST)*, 3(3):2298–2307.
- [Staab, 2014] Staab, W. (2014). Animal Vocalization Analysis : the gPLP (generalized perceptual linear prediction) model, <http://hearinghealthmatters.org/waynesworld/>.
- [ten Cate and Okanoya, 2012] ten Cate, C. and Okanoya, K. (2012). Revisiting the syntactic abilities of non-human animals: natural vocalizations and artificial grammar learning. *Philosophical transactions of the Royal Society of London. Series B, Biological sciences*, 367(1598):1984–94.
- [Titze, 1994] Titze, I. R. (1994). *Principles of voice production*. Englewood Cliffs, N.J. : Prentice Hall. Includes bibliographical references and index.
- [Tokuda et al., 2013] Tokuda, K., Nankaku, Y., Toda, T., Zen, H., Yamagishi, J., and Oura, K. (2013). Speech Synthesis Based on Hidden Markov Models. *Proceedings of the IEEE*, 101(5):1234–1252.
- [Tokuda et al., 2002] Tokuda, K., Zen, H., and Black, A. (2002). An HMM-based speech synthesis system applied to English. In *Speech Synthesis, 2002. Proceedings of 2002 IEEE Workshop on*, pages 2–5.
- [Welch and Bishop, 1997] Welch, G. and Bishop, G. (1997). An Introduction to the Kalman Filter. Technical report.
- [Young et al., 2006] Young, S., Evermann, G., Gales, M., and Hain, T. (2006). *The HTK Book (for HTK version 3)*.
- [Zen et al., 2006] Zen, H., Nose, T., Yamagishi, J., Sako, S., and Tokuda, K. (2006). The HMM-based Speech Synthesis System (HTS) Version 2 . 0 *. Technical report.